

IDENTIFYING HIDDEN TALENTS AND ABILITIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: this article highlights ideas about identifying the abilities and hidden talents of primary school students, their formation and methods that can be used for them.

Key words: development, talent, activity, strategy, academic, extra-academic hours, emotion, initiative, idea.

The main task of the primary school is to ensure the development of the child's personality. All-round development of the child occurs in two types of activities. First, any child grows up having mastered the past, that is, he is brought up with human experience formed through acquaintance with modern culture. This process is based on educational activities aimed at educating the child with knowledge and skills necessary for community life. Second, in the process of development, the child shows his capabilities independently through creative activity. It helps the child's initiative, self-awareness and realization of their own ideas aimed at creating new things. By performing this activity, it is possible to solve various problems of children and direct them to a specific goal. The fact that education and creative activity are not systematized in the same proportion creates problems in discovering hidden talents in children. A junior high school student is interested in the lively life around him, which opens new aspects of the world to him every day.

Children are always ready to do something useful. Therefore, it is necessary not only not to interfere with them, but also to bring out their talents and create an opportunity for them to engage in certain activities, - Jan Amos Comenius said. One of the main goals of educational reform is to discover the talents of each student. One of the main strategic goals of the concept of "Development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" is to create a system for the implementation of work with gifted children and talented youth, and in this way, primary education teachers face many tasks. Among the mysterious natural phenomena and gifted to us, children's talent is in the leading positions. Diagnosing and developing it is one of the problems of teachers.

Currently, the study of measures to eliminate it has increased and this is explained by social needs.

Most of us refer to our natural abilities when we say our talents. We do not think that talent is not born, it is formed. We enjoy the performance of our favorite musician on TV, but we don't see his hard work and efforts to become a superstar. In the same way, we can make children talented by forming talents based on their interests and abilities. Every student tends to be capable and talented in some direction. As a teacher, one of our main tasks is to get to know their abilities, explore their interests and use different strategies to bring out their hidden talents. Let's imagine that if we lose latent talents by not focusing on and developing them, it will be a great loss not only to the institution but also to the society. If we develop students' talents, we will make their future life a little easier.

Gifted children do not become the school's problem when schools respond individually to the needs of each student. It is the educational system that we call "normal" with gifted students that leads to the violation of their gifted standards and slows down the pace of education. This disorder is called "dysynchrony syndrome" and causes a disproportion between children's mental age and chronological age. Sometimes it is necessary to pay attention to this.

There is no doubt that the organizational structure of the school as we know it today is based on pragmatic criteria. The downside of these criteria is that mastery of only the standards required by the school system creates a sufficient understanding. It requires the same programs to be developed for all students at the same pace, a system that does not meet the needs of groups with learning that is different from that of regular groups. This requires teachers to take an independent approach to the formation of talents in their class.

Teachers play an important role in identifying hidden talents in students because they know their strengths and weaknesses by observing them. It is important for teachers to feel the hidden talents of students faster than their parents, relatives and friends and to teach them how to develop their talents.

Teachers can discover hidden talents in their students in different ways. We will see the expression of these methods in the following:

1. Monitoring students' hobbies. A teacher can discover a student's hidden talents by observing his hobbies and aptitudes for those hobbies. People usually love hobbies they are good at. People with a natural talent for a skill gravitate towards similar hobbies and find their calling. However, they give up these hobbies due to the fact that practical and pragmatic options are too difficult for them due to the inappropriate negative advice of their parents or relatives.

Teachers can identify a student's talent from their hobbies and advise them to take their hobbies seriously.

2. Ask about their feelings and interests. Teachers can get a feel for students' talents by asking them about their passions and interests. They can get candid feedback from students and observe students as they pursue their passions. Passionate kids often lose track of time and become completely oblivious to what's going on around them when they're engaged in an activity they really love. It's easy for teachers to get an idea of students' talents when they see students openly expressing their passions. Children's joy in small things describes their passion for life and creativity. Passion is the fuel that drives successful inventions. It is impossible to invent without the formation of hidden talents.

3. Organization of various contests and exhibitions. Teachers can discover the hidden talents of their students by organizing and encouraging them to participate in various competitions and exhibitions. They should convince the students not to indulge in competition and enjoy the competitions. The purpose of these competitions should not be to foster a sense of competition or competition among children, but to help them discover their hidden abilities and talents. It is advisable for teachers to organize some exhibitions and competitions such as science, arts and crafts that encourage students to participate in them and show their talents.

4. Organize a group trip and encourage students to think freely. Children usually come up with unique ideas when they're outdoors, and some downtime ensures their development. They are not afraid of being judged, so they express themselves freely. It is not surprising to see a child singing melodious songs without feeling any inhibitions. On such trips, children open up and leave their serious side behind. In order to discover the hidden talent of students, they need to be allowed to laugh heartily and express their thoughts freely.

5. Organization of extracurricular Olympiads. Teachers identify students' strengths in subjects by organizing science olympiads covering various criteria outside of school.

The ones we discussed above are academic skills. Non-academic skills are also important in developing students' talents. Why develop non-academic skills? For the comprehensive development of children, they need to know what to do and how to spend their time. Food for a healthy body and creativity for a healthy mind! Smart activities like reading stories, singing, and ice skating keep them busy, but they also enjoy non-academic learning and create space for creativity.

Sometimes teaching them the basics can be difficult, but just as we patiently wait for baby steps, the recipe for perfection must have the right ingredients.

In developing non-academic skills, students' parents need a lot of support. Because, basically, parents create the environment for this process. In order to identify the hidden talents and abilities of their children, the teacher should tell them the following: pay attention to what activities the children are inclined to, find extracurricular activities that support their interests and allow them to solve quizzes, rebuses, and encourage their creativity participate in training sessions.

Currently, modern education has its advantages in this area. For example, the existence of concepts in textbooks that form such characteristics as strengthening confidence, strengthening communication, expanding thinking ability, and gaining the position of a social person is the basis for the creativity of students.

We will create an opportunity for children to show their talents by creating an environment that meets their needs, observing them and involving them in various processes.

If a child's talent is discovered early, it will succeed faster with less difficulty on its way. Early detection of talents helps a person to do good things for society and to be a source of inspiration for others.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Benbow, C. P. & Lubinski, D. (1997). Intellectually Talented Children: How Can We Best Meet Their Needs? In Colangelo, N. & Davis, G. A. Handbook of Gifted Education. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
2. Милорадова Н.Г. Психология и педагогика:Учебник — М. Гардарики, 2006, 335 ст.
3. Leites Prodiges. Amazing children. 1990. 3.

